

IMPACT OF ND-YAG LASER DRILLING ON THE FATIGUE CHARACTERISTICS OF APC-2A/AS4 THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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SUMMARY: Both carbon fibre thermoset and thermoplastic materials can be drilled using a laser. This, however, results in significant damage to the material, but the extent to which this would reduce the fatigue life was not known. Studies were conducted to evaluate this for an aerospace application, which required a light-weight, but perforated, skin panel through which air could be sucked. The objective was to determine the impact on the fatigue life of quasi-isotropic APC-2A/AS4 due to Nd-YAG laser drilled holes (~120 µm diameter, spaced ~500 µm apart). Static tensile tests indicated a 29% reduction in strength. The *maximum stress versus cycles to failure (S-N)* relationship was represented by a power law function: $S = KN^m$. The laser drilling was seen to reduce the value of K (coefficient of fatigue strength), but the value of m (fatigue strength degradation exponent), which was determined from non-perforated specimens, was unchanged.

KEYWORDS: Nd-YAG laser drilling, APC-2A/AS4 thermoplastic laminates, fatigue damage, fatigue life

INTRODUCTION AND RATIONALE FOR STUDY

As skin friction accounts for roughly 50% of the total drag on a civil jet transport aircraft (in cruise), technologies that can substantially reduce the friction drag are of considerable interest to aircraft manufacturers and operators. Active Laminar Flow Control (LFC) is such a technique; it reduces drag by maintaining extended runs of laminar flow on an aircraft's surface (e.g. wing, empennage, engine nacelle) at Reynolds numbers normally associated with turbulent flow. The delay in transition of the boundary layer is achieved by bleeding modest amounts of air – from the external flow – through a perforated skin surface; the air is then ducted through a network of pipes and expelled (Fig. 1). (See Refs. 1–4, for example, for further details).

Titanium is the prime candidate material for the wing skin; however, the resulting weight penalty of this material makes it an unattractive option for the aircraft's engine nacelles or empennage. The work herein reported was conducted as part of a larger study to assess the viability of manufacturing the perforated skins from composite materials.

Carbon fibre reinforced composites have been successfully drilled by Excimer and Nd-YAG lasers^[5–8]. The author, with colleagues,^[7,8] previously investigated the effect of single and multi-pulse Nd-YAG laser drilling on the properties of carbon fibre epoxy test panels. The drilling process resulted in damage to the matrix around the holes due to the heat from the laser being conducted along the fibres. The resulting hole is not uniform in size – the laser entry hole diameter could be 2.5 (or more) times greater than that which occurs on the

laser entry side (Fig. 1). It was reported^[7] that the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) was reduced by 2%–48% depending on the drilling technique, material type and drilling pattern. A feature of the epoxy materials tested was that the resin damage around the holes lead to poor rain erosion resistance^[8]. And, for this reason, our attention turned to thermoplastics; some results of the ensuing studies are presented herein.

Fig. 1 Principle of laminar flow control with details of the perforated skin panel

OBJECTIVES

The objectives were to determine the effect on the static tensile strength and on the fatigue life of the thermoplastic composite material APC-2A/AS4 due to Nd-YAG (Neodymium-doped: Yttrium Aluminium Garnet) laser drilling (producing holes of $\sim 120 \mu\text{m}$ mean diameter, spaced $\sim 500 \mu\text{m}$ apart) and to represent the results using an empirical relationship.

TEST SPECIMENS

Production of Specimens

Specimens were manufactured from Cytec Fiberite APC-2A/AS4 (PEEK thermoplastic composite material in unidirectional form), stacked in an eight ply quasi-isotropic $[0/45/90/-45]_s$ sequence. Two batches of specimens were produced: laser perforated specimens and reference (i.e. non-perforated) specimens. All specimens measured 250 mm by 25 mm, with a nominal thickness of 1 mm; they were cut using a diamond coated saw. The width of each specimen was measured at several points along its length to ensure that any taper was within limits (determined from ASTM D 3039/ D 3039M–95a, Ref. 9). The only departure from the standard involved the thickness, which was reduced from 2 mm to 1 mm in order to facilitate the laser drilling.

Reference specimens were tabbed. Glass fibre epoxy tabs (25 mm wide) were bonded to the APC-2A/AS4 laminate using AF-3109-2 adhesive in such a way as to produce a controlled adhesive spew, which protruded from the tab at approximately 30° (Fig. 2). The specimens were cut to size after the tab strips were bonded to the consolidated panel.

Laser Drilling

The perforated specimens were drilled using an Nd-YAG laser with the laser head moving across the width of each specimen (Fig. 3). The nominal hole diameter (on the laser exit side) was set as 50 μm and the holes were spaced 500 μm apart. It was deemed undesirable to drill holes over the edge (or very close to the edge) of the specimens, as the holes would act as ‘notches’, possibly leading to premature failure. To avoid this, the specimens were first cut to the required size and then drilled such that each row began and ended between 3 and 10 hole diameters from the edge (Fig. 3). Subsequent rows were spaced $\sim 500 \mu\text{m}$ apart. The perforated specimens were not tabbed and a 10 mm gap was left between the drilled area and the point where the grips held the specimens (Fig. 4).

Fig. 2 Dimensions of non-perforated specimens

Fig. 3 Hole pattern ($d = \text{nominal hole diameter}$)

MEASUREMENT AND INSPECTION OF SPECIMENS

Prior to testing, each specimen was visually inspected for edge defects and other anomalies that could potentially affect its fatigue life. A digital vernier was used to measure the width and thickness of each specimen at three or more points along its length – mean values were used to determine the gross cross-sectional area of each specimen.

The drilled specimens were inspected using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). The resulting SEM images were used to study the hole shape and the heat affected zone surrounding the holes (Figs. 5 a-d). In some cases the holes were observed to have a figure-of-eight shape (as shown in the images selected for Fig. 5), but in other cases they were more rounded (Fig. 6). It is evident from the images that – in addition to the fibres that were cut to produce the holes – there was considerable damage to the matrix at the laser entry side. The

heat from the “plasma” around the laser head effectively burnt off the matrix in the vicinity of the holes (Figs. 5a and 5c). It was speculated that heat from the laser drilling was conducted along the carbon fibres further damaging the matrix. The laser exit images, however, did not show this type of damage, but it is evident that fibres were torn off the back face as the laser pulse burst through the specimen (Figs. 5b and 5d).

Fig. 4 Dimensions of perforated specimens

Fig. 5 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images of Nd-YAG laser drilled holes (Figs. a and c show laser entry; Figs. b and d show laser exit)

The SEM images were used to estimate the size of the holes on both the laser entry and laser exit sides of the specimens (illustrated in Fig. 6). A mean hole diameter of 186 μm on the laser entry side and 56 μm on the laser exit side was determined (Table 1). It should be noted that the stress results (discussed below) were based on the gross cross-section area and not the net area; in other words, the reference area disregarded the presence of the holes (this option is consistent with the recommendations of ASTM D 5766/D 5766M, Ref. 10).

Fig. 6 Measurement of hole dimensions using SEM images

Table 1 Hole diameters

	Laser entry (μm)	Laser exit (μm)	Average (μm)
Measurement 1	180	55	117.5
Measurement 2	185	55	120.0
Measurement 3	190	55	122.5
Measurement 4	185	60	122.5
Measurement 5	190	55	122.5
Average	186	56	121

TEST PROCEDURE – STATIC AND FATIGUE TESTS

Static Test Procedure

Static tests were conducted using a DARTEC 100 kN testing machine in accordance with ASTM D3039/ D 3039M-95a (Ref. 9). Five perforated and five non-perforated specimens were tested to determine their strength and stiffness. The specimen stiffness was based on the stroke reading of the testing rig – the results are thus approximate values, which could only be used as a guide in assessing the impact of laser drilling on the material’s stiffness.

The following test procedure was adopted: (1) The specimen was properly aligned with the machine loading axis and the grips, which were “composite” rated to provide a non-slip surface without inflicting jaw serration damage, were tightened with a gripping pressure of 6.9 MPa (1000 psi); (2) The specimen was loaded at a crosshead speed of 1.5 mm/min; (3) The stroke and load values were recorded at a rate of one reading per second; (4) The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) was calculated based on the mean of the failure loads of five tests (considering the reference area to be the gross cross-section area).

Fatigue Test Procedure

Constant-amplitude sinusoidal tension-tension fatigue tests were carried out using a DARTEC 100 kN testing machine, in accordance with the recommendations of ASTM D 3479/ D 3479M-96 (Ref. 11). The number of load cycles at which failure occurred was determined for each specimen, unless the endurance limit, which was set at one million cycles, was first reached.

The test procedure was as follows: (1) The specimen was properly aligned with the machine loading axis and the grips were tightened with a gripping pressure of 6.9 MPa (1000 psi); (2) The specimen was loaded with a load ratio (minimum/maximum load) of $R = 0.1$, at a frequency of 5 Hz, following a constant amplitude sinusoidal waveform; (3) Load values were continuously recorded and the number of cycles-to-failure were recorded.

RESULTS

Static Test Results

The static test results are presented below in Table 2; the laser drilling resulted in a 29% reduction in tensile strength and a ~10% reduction in stiffness.

Table 2 Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) and approximate stiffness

	Non-perforated		Perforated	
	UTS (MPa)	Approximate stiffness* (GPa)	UTS (MPa)	Approximate stiffness* (GPa)
Specimen 1	735	41.7	538	39.7
Specimen 2	702	44.7	542	39.4
Specimen 3	726	42.8	551	40.4
Specimen 4	730	42.8	503	38.1
Specimen 5	821	43.8	511	35.8
Average	743	43.2	529	38.7

*Note: Stiffness values are approximate values based on the stroke of the testing machine.

Fatigue Test Results

Five valid results for each specimen type (i.e. perforated and non-perforated) were sought for 90%, 80%, 70% and 60% of the Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS), and three for 50% UTS. The latter decision was based on the fact that specimens tested at 50% UTS were unlikely to fail before one million cycles. The results of specimens that broke at, or near, the tabs were disregarded; it was thus necessary to test more than five specimens at each load level.

All six of the specimens tested at 50% UTS reached the endurance limit, while two of the non-perforated and three of the perforated specimens reached this limit. The results are presented in Figs. 7–9 and are discussed below.

DISCUSSION

Non-perforated specimens

The mean values of *cycles to failure* for the non-perforated specimens were plotted against the *normalised maximum stress* (i.e. stress divided by UTS). The results were then compared to results obtained by Jen and Lee^[12] (as a partial validation of the work). The tests of Jen and Lee^[12] were performed using the identical material, also in a quasi-isotropic layup, but at two load ratios: $R = 0$ and $R = 0.2$ (the tests conducted by the author set $R = 0.1$). In Fig. 7 the results are compared and a reasonable correlation is evident.

The mean values of *cycles to failure* (ignoring invalid data) are given in the standard format of stress (S) versus cycles to failure (N) in Figs. 8 and 9. Jen and Lee^[12] demonstrate that the fatigue relationship (for this and other carbon fibre composite materials) may be expressed as a power law relationship:

$$S = KN^m \quad (1)$$

where K is the coefficient of fatigue strength, and
 m is the fatigue strength degradation exponent.

Curve fitting performed by Jen and Lee^[12] produced values that are shown as data sets 1 and 2 in Table 3. When plotted as a log–log relationship, a reasonable correlation with the results obtained by the author is evident (Fig. 8). This validated the use of the power law relationship.

Perforated specimens

The well-known Palmgren–Miner model indicates that materials that are damaged due to fatigue suffer a reduction in static strength. This is usually represented numerically as

$$\sum \frac{n_i}{N_i} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where n_i is the number of load cycles at the i^{th} load level, and
 N_i is the number of load cycles to cause failure at the i^{th} load level.

Graphically it can be interpreted as follows: on a log S versus log N plot, fatigue damage will move the trend line to the left, parallel with the original line. In other words, the value of K will be reduced, but m will be unchanged. It was speculated that this would be the case when comparing the perforated to the non-perforated specimens. In other words, the laser drilling would act as a fatigue “pre-damage” of the material. To test this notion, a trend line was drawn using the value of K determined for the non-perforated specimens, but reduced by 29% (i.e. the ratio of the mean UTS values, see Table 2). It is shown in Fig. 9 that with m unchanged a reasonable trend line through the perforated test data was achieved.

Table 3 Power law curve fitting parameters

	R	K (MPa)	m	Notes
Data set 1	0.0	935.2	0.0537	Source: Jen and Lee ^[12]
Data set 2	0.2	930.7	0.0498	Source: Jen and Lee ^[12]
Data set 3	0.1	776	0.0360	Author

Fig. 7 Comparison of averaged fatigue test results for non-perforated APC-2A/AS4

Fig. 8 Comparison of averaged fatigue test results for non-perforated APC-2A/AS4

Fig. 9 Comparison of averaged fatigue test results for perforated and non-perforated APC-2A/AS4 (trend lines ignore endurance limit values, i.e. 1 million cycles)

CONCLUSIONS

1. Nd-YAG laser drilling of APC-2A/AS4 test specimens, in an eight ply quasi-isotropic lay-up (1 mm thick), resulted in holes that had a mean hole diameter of 186 μm on the laser entry side and 56 μm on the laser exit side.
2. The “collateral” damage to the matrix around the holes (of the APC-2A/AS4 material) was less than that previously observed on carbon fibre epoxy material drilled in the identical manner.
3. Static tests indicated a $\sim 29\%$ reduction in tensile strength and a $\sim 10\%$ reduction in stiffness for the laser perforated specimens compared to the reference (i.e. non-perforated) specimens.
4. The *maximum stress* versus *cycles to failure* ($S-N$) relationship for the undamaged material – determined from the constant-amplitude tension-tension fatigue tests – could be expressed as a power law relationship: $S = KN^m$ where K is the coefficient of fatigue strength and m is the fatigue strength degradation exponent (previously reported by other researchers^[12]).
5. The fatigue-life characteristics ($S-N$ relationship) of the laser drilled specimens could be represented using the power law function with a reduced value of K , but unchanged value of m – the laser-drilling, in effect, acting as a fatigue pre-damage of the specimens.

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